

Image enhancing in poorly illuminated subterranean environments for MAV applications: A comparison study^{*}

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Abstract. This work focuses on a comprehensive study and evaluation of existing low-level vision techniques for low light image enhancement, targeting applications in subterranean environments. More specifically, an emerging effort is currently pursuing the deployment of Micro Aerial Vehicles in subterranean environments for search and rescue missions, infrastructure inspection and other tasks. A major part of the autonomy of these vehicles, as well as the feedback to the operator, has been based on the processing of the information provided from onboard visual sensors. Nevertheless, subterranean environments are characterized by a low natural illumination that directly affects the performance of the utilized visual algorithms. In this article, an novel extensive comparison study is presented among five State-of the-Art low light image enhancement algorithms for evaluating their performance and identifying further developments needed. The evaluation has been performed from datasets collected in real underground tunnel environments with challenging conditions from the onboard sensor of a MAV.

Keywords: Low Light Imaging · Image Enhancement · Subterranean MAV applications

1 Introduction

The technology of Micro Aerial Vehicles (MAVs) has shown increased levels of robustness in well defined and constrained lab environments. Recently, there is a large effort to operate these platforms outside of a lab and in real world, on site field scenarios. Until now, the majority of the consumer grade MAVs has been directed towards the photography-cinematography industry, taking advantage of their payload capacity and the stable flight characteristics. Nevertheless,

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an emerging trend is to integrate MAVs in the operation cycles of underground mines, as well as for search and rescue missions in general subterranean environments, trying to reduce the operating costs, increase the overall efficiency, while removing the human operator away from the harsh operating conditions, thus providing advanced tools for more effective decision making and overall mining operations [11].

In these application scenarios, multiple challenges arise before employing autonomous MAVs, mainly regarding the perception, planning and control of these air vehicles, such as the narrow passages, the reduced visibility due to rock falls, the dust existence, the uncertainty in localization, wind gusts and the overall lack of proper illumination. Within the related literature of MAVs in subterranean mine operations, several research efforts have been reported trying to address these challenging tasks. In [18] a visual inertial navigation framework has been proposed, to implement position tracking control of the platform. In this case, the MAV was controlled to follow obstacle free paths, while the system was experimentally evaluated in a real scale tunnel environment, simulating a coal mine, where the illumination challenge was assumed solved. In [3] a more realistic approach, compared to [18] regarding underground localization, has been performed. More specifically, a hexacopter equipped with a Visual Inertial (VI) sensor and a laser scanner was manually guided across a vertical mine shaft to collect data for post-processing. The extracted information from the measurements have been utilized to create a 3D mesh of the environment and localize the vehicle. Finally, in [12] the estimation, navigation, mapping and control capabilities for autonomous inspection of penstocks and tunnels using aerial vehicles has been studied by utilizing IMUs, cameras and lidar sensors.

Figure 1a) depicts a typical example of an underground tunnel with limited natural illumination. Inspired by the challenge of poor visibility in such environments, this work tries to identify the performance of the current state of the art methods in realistic and degraded environments with restricted access. Studying methods to enhance the quality of image data recorded on board of the MAV during the mission has a value for both the mission accomplishment as well as the data post processing for generating 3D models, identifying degradation in the area and general acquiring a direct visual feedback for the asset owners to contextualize the location of the damages found during the inspection task.

Generally, the quality of an image or a video sequence largely depends on the light conditions of the environment. For example strong light produces images with a wash out effect and weak light produce images that are not visible due to the darkness. For both of the cases, the contrast of the two images is extremely low and needs further modification in order to reveal the details of the images. These typical low light conditions occur in mines, usually due to the lack of proper illumination and in other underground or indoor dark environments, e.g. factories. In all these cases, even if it was possible and realistic to utilize a light on board of the MAV, in order to illuminate the surrounding area of interest, this would have drawbacks for the mission design due to: a) the limited weight that the MAV can lift, and b) the limited power supply that the MAV can support

Fig. 1: a) MAV with onboard illumination in a subterranean area with complete lack of natural illumination sources. b) Image of low light conditions in a mine captured by the camera on board a MAV.

with the corresponding impact on the flight duration. A characteristic example of such a low light image capturing conditions acquired from a camera on a MAV is displayed in Figure 1b). Image enhancement techniques [7] have received great attention mostly because of their simplicity as also their effectiveness. Even nowadays in the era of Deep Learning (DL), efforts are being made to enhance images especially in the case of low light conditions [2].

This work is aligned with the vision of deploying aerial robotic platforms in subterranean environments, and it focuses on the study and understanding on how the low-level image enhancement mechanisms can be incorporated in the application scenarios of MAVs flying in low light environments. The contribution of the proposed work is two-folded. Initially, this article presents a thorough performance analysis of State-of-the-Art methods on datasets collected from real underground environments with limited visibility. The second contribution stems from the collected datasets, which include images with varying illumination levels that correspond to real environment, compared to artificially generate low light images. They have been generated by using a low cost aerial platform equipped with a single camera that can be considered as a consumable and easily replaceable in areas that have limited access to the public and there are not many similar datasets available in the literature, where the presented analysis provides insights to bring these algorithms a step closer to real life applications.

The rest of this article is organized as it follows. In Section 2 the image processing methods for low light image enhancement are summarized, while in Sections 3 and 4 the data collection procedure and the study evaluations of the State-of-the-Art methods in field trials are described respectively. Finally, the concluding remarks and future work are presented in Section 5.

2 Methodology

In this article five methods have been utilized for the image low light enhancement and in the sequel each one of them is going to be briefly described.

LIME [4] is a method that belongs to the Retinex-based category [1,6], which intends to enhance a low-light image by estimating its illumination map. However one of the fundamental differences from other Retinex based methods that are

based on decomposing the recorded image into the reflectance and illumination component, is the fact that it estimates one of the two components, namely the illumination. This has the advantage that it reduces the solution space and thus reduces the overall computation cost. The first step of the method is to estimate the illumination map computing the maximum intensity for each one of the pixels of the three channels (Red, Green, Blue) of the color image. Then, a refinement step is employed to better estimate the illumination map by introducing an Augmented Lagrangian Multiplier.

The goal of the Joint Low-Light enhancement and denoising method [15] is to enhance a low light image, while in parallel tries to minimize the inherent noise. The method is based on the Retinex category and decomposes the image into a reflectance and illumination map and a smoothed illumination map, with a noise free reflectance map, is computed. This is achieved by initially estimating the illumination map and then independently estimating the reflectance map. After the extraction of the smoothed illumination map, a large fraction of the noise is still present in the reflectance map, which is suppressed in the sequel by using weighted matrices.

The LECARM [16] method uses the nonlinear Camera Response Function (CRF) in order to reduce distortions to the enhancement and thus it leads to a significant reduction in the visual quality. In this approach, initially it is employed a fixed response curve in order to obtain the parameters of the CRF function. Then the second step in this methodology is the estimation of the illumination map by using the LIME method [4] and in the sequel the estimated exposure ratio map can be extracted from that, since it is inversely proportional to the illumination map.

The MSR [13,14] method is another method based on the Retinex model [8]. It combines the retinex dynamic range compression and color constancy with a color restoration filter that provides excellent color rendition.

Finally, in the last method [20] a two level exposure fusion approach in order to compute, as accurate as possible, the contrast and light enhancement is introduced. The method first computes a weight matrix for the image fusion step by using the illumination map that will be estimated. The camera response model is then computed and the best exposure ratio is computed for regions where the original images are under exposed. The final image is fused with the enhanced image by using the weight matrix.

3 Dataset Overview

The proposed study of image processing techniques in dark environments has been evaluated by using datasets collected from actual flights of two custom designed aerial platforms shown in Figure 2 and from two different locations in Sweden. The rest of the section provides a thorough description of the visited underground areas.

Fig. 2: Aerial platforms used for the dataset collection. On the left column is the platform used for the 1st dataset and on the right column is the platform used on the 2nd dataset.

3.1 Description of Datasets

The first dataset was collected inside a tunnel under Mjölkuddsberget mountain located at Luleå, Sweden. The selected environment, which resembles an underground mine tunnel, was pitch dark without any external illumination, while the tunnel surfaces consisted by uneven rock formations. The dimensions of the testing tunnel area were $100 \times 2.5 \times 3 \text{ m}^3$, capturing the camera sequences, while the MAV was following the path along the tunnel. Furthermore, the tunnel lack the presence of strong magnetic fields, while small particles were floating in the air during the flights. The aerial platform has been equipped with one 10 W LED light bar pointing towards the field of view of the camera to illuminate its surroundings. In more details, this light bar was set to different illumination levels (luminous flux per unit area or lux) varying from 2000 lux to 400 lux. The camera used in the dataset sequences was the FOXEER Box ¹ that was recording with a resolution of 1920×1080 at 60 fps. Figure 3 depicts representative snapshots of the dataset, where the dominating darkness in the surrounding environment is evident.

The second dataset was collected in an area 790 m deep in an underground mine in Sweden without any natural illumination sources. Furthermore, the underground tunnels did not have strong corrupting magnetic fields, while their morphology resembled an *S* shape environment with small inclination. Overall, the field trial area had width, height and length dimensions of 6 m, 4 m, and 150 m respectively. The MAV is equipped with two 10 W LED light bars in both front arms for providing additional illumination for the looking forward camera. In more details, this light bar was set to different illumination levels (luminous flux per unit area or lux) varying from 400 lux to 40 lux. During the data collection, the GoPro7 visual sensor has been used with resolution of 3840×2160 pixels with 60 fps. Figure 3 depicts representative snapshots of the dataset, where the dominating darkness in the surrounding environment is evident.

¹ <http://foxeer.com/Foxeer-4K-Box-Action-Camera-SuperVision-g-22>

Fig. 3: In the left column are depicted representative snapshots from the first Dataset, while in the right column are depicted representative snapshots from the second Dataset.

3.2 Evaluation Strategies

The merit of the dataset is the fact that it considers non ideal conditions captured in real low light environments with sensors that are commonly used in MAV applications. The datasets have been captured from an aerial vehicle flying along subterranean tunnels. In the performed field trials, it was not possible to capture images with ground truth illumination to match the actual images recorded in the dataset that have low illumination levels, since the MAV motion was slightly different in every run. The popular full-reference PSNR/SSIM [5] metrics found in the literature, for evaluating the enhancement methods, have limited evaluation applicability in practice. Therefore, to complement the evaluation process this work refers to two no-Reference IQA models: 1) BLind Image Integrity Notator using DCT-Statistics (BLIINDS2) [17] and 2) Naturalness Image Quality Evaluator (NIQE) [10], 3) Blind/Referenceless Image Spatial Quality Evaluator (BRISQUE) [9], 4) Perception based Image Quality Evaluator (PIQE) [19]. The no-Reference method provides as an outcome a score $\in [0, 100]$, where the lowest value indicates a better performance.

The described datasets have been used for the method evaluation. More specifically, the first set of evaluation images is described as *Set1* and is derived from part of *dataset2*. The *Set1* includes 200 frames captured with 40lux illumination measured from 1m distance. The MAV was flying manually following a straight path. The second set of evaluation images is described as *Set2* and is derived from part of *dataset2*. The *Set2* includes 200 frames captured with

100lux illumination measured from 1m distance. The MAV was flying manually following the tunnel. Finally, another part from the *dataset2* has been extracted into the *Set3* where it includes 200 frames captured with 200lux illumination measured from 1m distance. The MAV was flying autonomously following the S-shaped tunnel path. All images in the datasets have been exported from the videos recorded onboard and have been saved in a JPEG compression format. Additionally, all frames have been down-sampled to $960pixels \times 540pixels$ for reducing the overall computation time.

For a fair comparison, all methods have been evaluated in Windows 10 MATLAB environment in a machine with 2.69GHz CPU and 12G RAM.

4 Evaluation

This Section describes the evaluation results of the five State-of-the-Art methods available online, namely: 1) BIMEF ², 2) LECARM ³, 3) JED ⁴, 4) Multi-scaleRetinex ⁵, and 5) LIME ⁶.

The evaluation process is divided in two parts: a) quantitative evaluation, and b) subjective-qualitative evaluation. Table 1 presents the BLIINDS2 and NIQE metrics for all methods for a number of 10 images from Set1, Set2 and Set3, while Table 2 presents the BRISQUE and PIQE metrics for all methods for 200 images from Set1, Set2 and Set3. By inspecting the tables it is observed that for different metrics different methods perform better. The performance is also varying among different datasets for the same method. When it comes to no-reference metrics the results become less consistent. Such an inconsistency between no-reference evaluations is a point raised in this work and should be addressed in a task oriented manner for different application scenarios.

Table 1: Average no-Reference evaluation results of low light enhancement algorithms

	Set1		Set2		Set3	
	Bliinds2	Niqe	Bliinds2	Niqe	Bliinds2	Niqe
BIMEF	29.8421	19.2128	87.3000	21.0303	33.9500	19.1589
LECARM	30.9000	19.0942	16.1500	20.8437	34.7000	18.8645
JED	34.6500	19.3555	21.9500	25.2385	36.3500	19.5826
MSR	34.6250	16.5409	37.6000	19.8599	40.9000	16.9791
LIME	33.4500	18.4797	19.9000	19.3274	36.9000	18.3015

² <https://github.com/baidut/BIMEF>

³ <https://github.com/baidut/LECARM>

⁴ <https://github.com/baidut/OpenCE/tree/master/others>

⁵ <https://github.com/baidut/BIMEF/tree/master/lowlight>

⁶ <https://github.com/baidut/BIMEF/tree/master/lowlight>

Table 2: Average no-Reference evaluation results of low light enhancement algorithms

	Set1		Set2		Set3	
	Brisque	Piqe	Brisque	Piqe	Brisque	Piqe
BIMEF	32.2073	16.9229	37.0642	29.8044	45.9678	12.8824
LECARM	35.6660	15.3142	36.1718	29.1353	46.0225	10.2393
JED	51.1892	39.2722	39.7473	48.1605	50.2417	42.7230
MSR	40.8146	16.2568	19.4552	32.5144	46.6340	10.5247
LIME	40.0704	13.6910	39.3943	40.2375	46.8235	9.4447

Although the methods have been evaluated using the above no-Reference metrics it is not evident how the algorithms perform in reality and their applicability in various MAV missions. To this end, Figure 4 visualize the resulting outcome when employing the methods using the collected datasets. Three different frames have been selected from each set of images (Set1, Set2 and Set3), which are representative from such tunnel environments. From this Figure it is shown that all methods reveal further details from the environment by showing the tunnel width. Although MultiscaleRetinex adds to many artifacts and noise, its applicability fits for visual feedback to the operator, thus extending the surroundings perceived from the aerial vehicle. Moreover, they fit for navigation tasks that process the darkness of the tunnels, by revealing the local geometry of the tunnels showing walls and floors. However, the images are noisy for 3D reconstruction and place recognition methods.

Fig. 4: Qualitative results for the human visual perception.

4.1 Future Directions

From the presented results it is evident that there is room for further developments in the fields of aerial robotics and the low-level image processing. More specifically, since in real applications it is hard to capture ground truth data,

there is a need to propose new metrics that capture the performance of the methods within the desired application scenarios. The use of low light image enhancement algorithms should be task oriented, where different algorithms could fit better in different applications. Few application scenarios that are currently pursued include enhanced visual feedback to the operator, 3D reconstruction, object detection in dark environments, visual place recognition for navigation tasks, as well as general vision based navigation and planning tasks. A major parameter that affects the performance of the methods is the geometry of the tunnels. In the case of narrow tunnels the illumination is spread in the local vicinity (walls, floor and ceiling) of the platform, assisting the usage of the methods. On the contrary, wide tunnels are more challenging since usually, the onboard illumination is absorbed from the void in the front of the aerial vehicle and the local vicinity of the platform is weakly illuminated. In this work the methods have been applied in the most challenging case of wide tunnels.

5 Conclusions

This work focuses on a comprehensive study and evaluation of existing low-level vision techniques for low light image enhancement, targeting MAV applications in underground environments. Subterranean environments are characterized by low natural illumination, which directly affects the performance of visual algorithms. In this work, an extensive comparison study has been presented among five State-of-the-Art low light image enhancement algorithms to evaluate their performance and further developments. The evaluation has been performed from datasets collected in real underground tunnel environments with challenging conditions from the onboard sensor of a MAV. From the presented results it is shown that there is no single-best low-light enhancement method for all criteria. The inconsistency in the results is complicated depicting that the method performance depends of the prior it uses and the design choices. Future works should focus and optimize on evaluation criteria that are task oriented aligned with higher level tasks.

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